

EFFECTIVE METHODS IN ENGLISH TEACHING FOR MILITARY EDUCATORS

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Abstract: *Teaching English in the military system is at the same time a difficult and a rewarding job. The challenges English teachers encounter nowadays are mainly related to designing or adapting instructional methods that would function efficiently within the specific framework of the military linguistic context. This article aims at presenting the practical effects of three such different methods: the interactive, the situational, and the task-based methods which are the best methods to be used for military English teaching.*

Keywords: *military English teaching, interactive method, case-study, teaching effects, task-based learning*

Learning is an internal process, which is crucially depend upon the knowledge. The learners already have ability and motivation to use it. However, learning is not just a mental process, it is a process of negotiation between individuals and the society. It is obvious that the greatest teaching effects can be achieved

under the teaching methods, which combine teachers' presentation with learners' production. These methods hold an efficient balance between receptive skills (including listening and reading) and productive skills (including writing and speaking).

Nowadays a teacher of foreign language must take into consideration the strategy which is

based on the objectives of the course, the depth and faults of the subject matter, the physical environment in the classroom, and the capabilities of cadets to learn given the approach. The strategy selected must be based on the faculty's preference and its suitability for helping them to meet the objectives. Palmer believes that "good teaching comes from the identity and the integrity of the teacher [1]." Or in other words, "we teach who we are". It is teacher's connection with his or her cadets that creates the learning environment. Therefore, teachers should not adopt a strategy, however well-intentioned, if they do not believe that it is consistent with whom they are.

Teachers, then, need to consider three different factors when developing an instructional program:

1) content, or the skills and knowledge that the students must learn in the program;

2) instructional strategies that would contribute to learning given the content; and 3) the instructor's analysis of the best use of strategies, given the content, to support learning.

We have chosen for analysis three different instructional methods (the interactive, the situational and the task-based learning methods),

each having its advantages and its disadvantages.

➤ **The Interactive Method**

This method is based and characterized by interaction between teachers and cadets. If we are to consider the cultivation of communicative skills the primary goal of foreign language learning, then interaction is a must in the classroom. Real communication is defined as interaction between people; in the same way, linguistic interaction is seen as a collaborative activity and therefore classroom teaching and learning activities must be interactive in nature. Interactive language teaching stresses the importance of providing learners with opportunities to interact directly with the target language, to acquire it by using it rather than learning it by studying it. It shifts the focus from teacher centred to a cadet centred activities; the teacher is no longer the sage on the stage but a facilitator, a manager, an independent participant, making the process of learning an easy task and helping students clear away roadblocks and finding their own way through different communicative situations. The cadets are expected to cooperate by listening to each other, sharing information, negotiating meaning, solving problems, dealing with real life situations in the target language.

The interactive method is based on some fundamental teaching principles: the initiation of interaction (usually done by the teacher), achieved with the help of various questioning strategies (knowledge questions, comprehension questions, application questions, inference questions, analysis questions, synthesis questions, etc); the engaging of the cadets, meaning the application of active learning principles through discussions, debates, pair work and group work activities; the promotion of the appropriate language strategies, which requires that educators possess a solid theoretical background enabling them to promote cadets' awareness and their active involvement in the learning process (memory strategies, cognitive strategies, compensation strategies, metacognitive strategies, social strategies, affective strategies, etc.) [2].

Case studies have proven to be an extremely effective method and debate on issues for which definite solutions do not exist. The follow-up activity for this reading is a situational task, in which the cadets are instructed to use a map and draw the tactical movements of the armies involved in the conflict. The learners are then put into groups of three or four and asked to discuss,

analyze and evaluate the military strategies used. This activity is a very complex one, allowing a diverse usage of language, language functions and skills.

➤ **The Situational Method**

Situational teaching is an adaptation of the various strategies in which the instructor uses a wide range of teacher-centred and student-centered methods depending on the course content and the instructor's use of active learning strategies. Like with any active learning method, instructors should encourage their cadets to a course, analyzing the problem, creating a solution, and explaining and defending the solution. Consequently, situational learning depends on two claims: it must be contextualized, and should not be abstract or general; new knowledge is to be presented within a realistic context.

Usually, the teacher prepares materials that are explained to the cadets' item by item in class and lays stress on teaching specific military terminology in context, analyzing and explaining difficult sentences, and increasing students' language and information input. With the help of the situations designed by the teacher and the context, students are able to understand the language presented to them and relate it to their own professional

experience in the military. The best type of activities that fit this method is the role plays and simulations which task the learners to assume the part of a participant in a real-life context and solve the situation using linguistic patterns. The next example is a simulation used to practice vocabulary targeted to the topic.

➤ **The Task-Based Learning Method**

In recent years, task-based learning has grown steadily in popularity. The teachers' role in this approach is basically one of central and active importance. The teacher sets the framework of the activity and guides the students into accomplishing the given task. The teacher cleverly designs all the teaching points into diverse "tasks" according to the teaching requirements. Guided by the teacher, the cadets would accomplish those tasks one by one by themselves. There are three steps in the teaching process: giving tasks – accomplishing tasks – evaluation. In the first step, the teacher would make sure that all those tasks, including reading, writing, new words understanding and translating, are clearly assigned and understood. In the second step, the teacher would help the students to accomplish those tasks by supplying various methods or hints. In the last step, the teacher checks

what the students have accomplished, focusing mostly on productive skills.

This approach suits our target population very well, since our students are adults who take full responsibility for their own learning. They are used to being left alone when studying in their own way and at their own pace, while the teacher acts as a modeller, controller, direction setter, monitor, corrector, etc. It is a great strategy to use with military students who should be educated to take the learning matter into their own hands, as learning is a continuous, life-lasting process and they will often have to adapt to new environments where the guiding authority – the teacher – might not always be present. For example, drawing a map while listening to a tape, listening to an instruction and performing the command it describes can be referred to as tasks. They may or may not involve the production of language. They require a clarification in terms of what is meant by completion of the task and what the teacher expects to be the desired outcome. Such activities are successfully used in our military classrooms, with the particular purpose of practising cognitive and language skills at the same time.

In conclusion, Military English teaching is ESP teaching. Some

cadets may like it; many more feel nervous to study it. Under such circumstances, it is better for the teacher to communicate with the cadets all through the teaching process, helping them to get rid of the nervousness, and encouraging them to use English as a tool to do their research in military field.

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